

Supplementary Figure S4. Micro-CT reconstruction animation of the eyes of rostellariid *Rostellariella delicatula* and aporrhaid *Aporrhais pespelecani*. Available in the Dryad Digital Repository, at: https://datadryad.org/stash/share/Nm-w5jOQWmN1Ny5puAKns7i6Lv_fghcxsIDSPD1y29s [doi:10.5061/dryad.pnvx0k6v0].